

**ENTITLEMENT TO GRANT OF BAIL UNDER SECTION 167 OF
CRPC IN CASES OF NON-BAILABLE AND NON-COGNIZABLE
OFFENCES: LEGAL DISCOURSE**

by

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ABSTRACT

The Code of Criminal Procedure 1973 (hereinafter 'CRPC') provides procedure related to the prosecution in criminal cases all over the India. CRPC classifies the offences into cognizable and non-cognizable for the purpose of authority of the police officer to arrest the accused. A cognizable offence empowers the police officer to arrest any person without warrant from the Magistrate whereas a non-cognizable offence requires the police officer to obtain warrant before the arrest. A cognizable offence could be bailable as well as non-bailable, as provided in Schedule I to the CRPC. Similarly, a non-cognizable offence could be bailable as well as non-bailable. This paper endeavours to state the provision in respect of grant of bail in cognizable offences. It further endeavours to contemplate the conditions for grant of statutory bail in case of cognizable as well as non-cognizable offences under section 167 of CRPC.

KEYWORDS: Filing of Charge-sheet; non cognizable offences; regular bail; Default bail; precedence.

INTRODUCTION:

The Code of Criminal Procedure 1973 (hereinafter 'CRPC') provides procedure related to the prosecution in criminal cases all over the India. It provisions related to appointment of prosecution officer, jurisdiction of judges in different stages of criminal trial, the types of trial, i.e. Warrant trial, Sessions trial, summons trial, and the summary trial. It further provides the limitation for disposal of a criminal trial in cases of petty offences, the provision of legal aid, provision for probation for accused who have not attained twenty one years of age and the principle of plea bargaining as a measure for quantification of the sentence. This paper endeavours to state the provision in respect of grant of bail in cognizable offences. It further endeavours to contemplate the conditions for grant of statutory bail in case of cognizable as well as non-cognizable offences under section 167 of CRPC.

CONDITIONS FOR THE GRANT OF BAIL UNDER SECTION 437 OF CRPC:

CRPC classifies the offences¹ into cognizable and non-cognizable for the purpose of authority of the police officer to arrest the accused. A cognizable offence² empowers the police officer to arrest any person without warrant from the Magistrate whereas a non-cognizable offence³ requires the police officer to take warrant before the arrest. A cognizable offence could be bailable⁴ as well as non-bailable, as provided in Schedule I to the CRPC. Similarly, a non-cognizable offence could be bailable as well as non-bailable. Section 57 of CRPC requires the police officer making an arrest without warrant to take or send the person arrested before a Magistrate having jurisdiction in the case, or before the officer in charge of a police station. It reads:

Section 56: Person arrested to be taken before Magistrate or officer in charge of police station.—A police officer making an arrest without warrant shall, without unnecessary delay and subject to the provisions herein contained as to bail, take or send the person arrested

¹ Section 2(n) of CRPC defines an offence and states: offence means any act or omission made punishable by any law for the time being in force and includes any act in respect of which a complaint may be made under section 20 of the Cattle-trespass Act, 1871 (1 of 1871);

² Section 2(c) of CRPC defines a cognizable offence and states: cognizable offence means an offence for which, and —cognizable case means a case in which, a police officer may, in accordance with the First Schedule or under any other law for the time being in force, arrest without warrant;

³ Section 2(l) of CRPC defines a non-cognizable offence and states: non-cognizable offence means an offence for which, and —non-cognizable case means a case in which, a police officer has no authority to arrest without warrant;

⁴ Section 2(a) of CRPC defines a bailable offence and states: bailable offence means an offence which is shown as bailable in the First Schedule, or which is made bailable by any other law for the time being in force; and —non-bailable offence means any other offence;

before a Magistrate having jurisdiction in the case, or before the officer in charge of a police station.

Section 57 of CRPC (in pursuance of section 56 of CRPC) requires the police officer making the arrest to produce the person arrested before the Magistrate within a period of twenty four hours after making the arrest. It reads:

Section 57. Person arrested not to be detained more than twenty-four hours.—No police officer shall detain in custody a person arrested without warrant for a longer period than under all the circumstances of the case is reasonable, and such period shall not, in the absence of a special order of a Magistrate under section 167, exceed twenty-four hours exclusive of the time necessary for the journey from the place of arrest to the Magistrate's Court.

Clause (2) to Section 167 of CRPC empowers the Magistrate to whom the accused is forwarded under section 57 of CRPC to authorise the detention of the accused person for a term not exceeding fifteen days in the whole. The proviso to clause (2) to section 167 of CRPC further empowers the Magistrate having jurisdiction in the case to authorise the detention of the accused person, otherwise than in the custody of the police, beyond the period of fifteen days, if he is satisfied that adequate grounds exist for doing so, but no Magistrate shall authorise the detention of the accused person in custody under this paragraph for a total period exceeding-

(i) ninety days, where the investigation relates to an offence punishable with death, imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a term not less than ten years;

(ii) sixty days, where the investigation relates to any other offence,

and on the expiry of the said period period of ninety days, or sixty days, as the case may be, the accused person shall be released on bail if he is prepared to and does furnish bail, and every person released on bail under this sub-section shall be deemed to be so released under the provisions of Chapter XXXIII for the purposes of that Chapter; ...⁵Thus, the grant of bail

⁵ clause (2) to section 167 of CRPC states:

The Magistrate to whom an accused person is forwarded under this section may, whether he has or has not jurisdiction to try the case, from time to time, authorise the detention of the accused in such custody as such Magistrate thinks fit, for a term not exceeding fifteen days in the whole; and if he has no jurisdiction to try the case or commit it for trial, and considers further detention unnecessary, he may order the accused to be forwarded to a Magistrate having such jurisdiction:

Provided that—

(a) the Magistrate may authorise the detention of the accused person, otherwise than in custody of the police, beyond the period of fifteen days, if he is satisfied that adequate grounds exist for doing so, but no Magistrate

under section 167 of CRPC relates solely for cognizable offences and such grant of bail is deemed valid for the provisions of section 437 of CRPC.⁶

Section 437 of CRPC provides 'when bail may be taken in case of non-bailable offence'. Section 437 of CRPC states that a person arrested for commission of any non-bailable offence or detained without warrant may be released on bail by the Court where he is so produced subject to certain conditions like the severity of the offence committed and the antecedents of the offender. In *Virupakshappa Gouda v. State of Karnataka*⁷, Hon'ble Supreme Court referred following cases in order to provide the conditions for grant of bail:

The court has to keep in mind what has been stated in *Chaman Lal v. State of U.P. and another*⁸. The requisite factors are: (i) the nature of accusation and the severity of punishment in case of conviction and the nature of supporting evidence; (ii) reasonable apprehension of tampering with the witness or apprehension of threat to the complainant; and (iii) prima facie satisfaction of the court in support of the charge. In *Prasanta Kumar Sarkar v. Ashis Chatterjee and another*⁹, it has been opined that while exercising the power for grant of bail, the court has to keep in mind certain circumstances and factors. We may usefully reproduce the said passage:-

shall authorise the detention of the accused person in custody under this paragraph for a total period exceeding—

(i) ninety days, where the investigation relates to an offence punishable with death, imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a term of not less than ten years;

(ii) sixty days, where the investigation relates to any other offence,

and, on the expiry of the said period of ninety days, or sixty days, as the case may be, the accused person shall be released on bail if he is prepared to and does furnish bail, and every person released on bail under this subsection shall be deemed to be so released under the provisions of Chapter XXXIII for the purposes of that Chapter;

(b) no Magistrate shall authorise detention of the accused in custody of the police under this section unless the accused is produced before him in person for the first time and subsequently every time till the accused remains in the custody of the police, but the Magistrate may extend further detention in judicial custody on production of the accused either in person or through the medium of electronic video linkage;

(c) no Magistrate of the second class, not specially empowered in this behalf by the High Court, shall authorise detention in the custody of the police.

Explanation I.—For the avoidance of doubts, it is hereby declared that, notwithstanding the expiry of the period specified in paragraph (a), the accused shall be detained in custody so long as he does not furnish bail.

Explanation II.—If any question arises whether an accused person was produced before the Magistrate as required under clause (b), the production of the accused person may be proved by his signature on the order authorising detention or by the order certified by the Magistrate as to production of the accused person through the medium of electronic video linkage, as the case may be.

Provided further that in case of a woman under eighteen years of age, the detention shall be authorised to be in the custody of a remand home or recognised social institution.

⁶ proviso (b) to clause (2) to section 167 of CRPC.

⁷ (2017) 5 SCC 406 at 411-412, para 15 and 16.

⁸ (2004) 7 SCC 525.

⁹ (2010) 14 SCC 496.

“9....among other circumstances, the factors which are to be borne in mind while considering an application for bail are:

- (i) whether there is any prima facie or reasonable ground to be believed that the accused had committed the offence.
- (ii) nature and gravity of the accusation;
- (iii) severity of the punishment in the event of conviction;
- (iv) danger of the accused absconding or fleeing, if released on bail;
- (v) character, behaviour, means, position and standing of the accused;
- (vi) likelihood of the offence being repeated;
- (vii) reasonable apprehension of the witnesses being influenced; and
- (viii) danger, of course, of justice being thwarted by grant of bail.”

In *Central Bureau of Investigation v. Vijay Sai Reddy*¹⁰, the Court had reiterated the principle by observing thus:- “While granting bail, the court has to keep in mind the nature of accusation, the nature of evidence in support thereof, the severity of the punishment which conviction will entail, the character of the accused, circumstances which are peculiar to the accused, reasonable possibility of securing the presence of the accused at the trial, reasonable apprehension of the witnesses being tampered with, the larger interests of the public/State and other similar considerations. It has also to be kept in mind that for the purpose of granting bail, the legislature has used the words reasonable grounds for believing instead of the evidence which means the court dealing with the grant of bail can only satisfy itself as to whether there is a genuine case against the accused and that the prosecution will be able to produce prima facie evidence in support of the charge. It is not expected, at this stage, to have the evidence establishing the guilt of the accused beyond reasonable doubt.”

SECTION 167 OF CRPC HAS PRECEDENCE OVER SECTION 437 OF CRPC IN MATTERS OF GRANT OF BAIL:

¹⁰ (2013) 7 SCC 452 at 465, para 34.

This section endeavours to analyse the provisions related to grant of bail provided in chapter XXXIII of CRPC entitled 'Provisions as to Bail and Bonds'. Section 167 of CRPC provides the period for pre-trial detention and therefore, the weight of section 167 of CRPC could be contemplated on following rationales:

1. A person accused of a bailable offence, whether it is cognizable or non-cognizable, is entitled for grant of bail under section 436 of CRPC;
2. A person who is in custody for a non-bailable offence which is classified as a non-cognizable offence in Schedule I of CRPC is entitled for bail within the period of ninety days or sixty days, as the case may be, as stipulated in section 167 of CRPC if the Magistrate is satisfied for grant of bail under the provisions of section 437 of CRPC. This is for the reason that section 167 of CRPC is applicable specifically to cognizable offences and the proviso (a) to clause (2) to section 167 of CRPC confers maximum limit for pre-trial detention of ninety days in case the offence is punishable with death, imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a term not exceeding ten years. It would be pertinent to note that a cognizable offence authorizes the police officer to arrest the offender without warrant from the magistrate whereas a non-cognizable offence requires the police officer to obtain the warrant of arrest before making making the arrest. This shows that a cognizable offence is comparatively accorded more weight in terms of seriousness of its impact than a non-cognizable offence. Therefore, the provision for grant of bail that empowers a Magistrate having jurisdiction in a case related to the cognizable offence would ipso facto apply in cases of grant of bail for non-cognizable offences. This means that in cases of non-bailable offences, where the offence is non-cognizable, the accused is entitled to grant of bail within the period stipulated in proviso (a) to clause (2) of section 167 of CRPC as a general rule. However, this general rule is subject to the parameters provided in clause (1) to section 437 of CRPC.
3. A person who is in custody in case of non-bailable offence which is classified as a cognizable offence under Schedule I to CRPC, the provision for parameters for grant of bail is provided in clause (1) to section 437 of CRPC. But such parameters are particular in nature and as a general rule, the limitation for grant of bail is determined by the period of ninety days or sixty days, as the case may be, stipulated in proviso (a) to clause (2) of section 167 of CRPC. The reason for applicability of section 167 of CRPC is probably the specific period for pre-trial detention provided in it. It would be

pertinent to refer the observation of Hon'ble Supreme Court in *Serious Fraud Investigation Office v. Rahul Modi and others*¹¹. The Court stated in concluding paragraphs of its judgement that:

"It is not necessary to repeat that in both Madar Sheikh (supra) and M. Ravindran (supra), this Court expressed its view that non-filing of the charge-sheet within the statutory period is the ground for availing the indefeasible right to claim bail under Section 167(2), CrPC. The conundrum relating to the custody of the accused after the expiry of 60 days has also been dealt with by this Court in Bhikamchand Jain (supra). It was made clear that the accused remains in custody of the Magistrate till cognizance is taken by the relevant court."¹²

Similarly the Court stated: **So long as an application has been made for default bail on expiry of the stated period before time is further extended to the maximum period of 180 days, default bail, being an indefeasible right of the accused under the first proviso to Section 167(2), kicks in and must be granted.**¹³

However, the right to statutory bail under section 167 of CRPC is subject to the condition of fulfillment of bail. Hon'ble Supreme Court observed:

"Notwithstanding the order of default bail passed by the Court, by virtue of Explanation I to Section 167(2), the actual release of the accused from custody is contingent on the directions passed by the competent Court granting bail. If the accused fails to furnish bail and/or comply with the terms and conditions of the bail order within the time stipulated by the Court, his continued detention in custody is valid."

CONCLUSION:

Section 167 of the CRPC provides for the provision of default bail before the filing of charge sheet¹⁴ in case of a cognizable offence. This paper concludes that the provision

¹¹ Criminal Appeal no. 185-186 of 2022, available at: https://main.sci.gov.in/supremecourt/2019/20286/20286_2019_35_1501_33176_Judgement_07-Feb-2022.pdf (last visited 27.02.2022).

¹² Para 15 of *ibid*.

¹³ *Bikramjit Singh v. State of Punjab*, 2020 SCC OnLine SC 824, decided on 12.10.2020, available at: <https://www.sconline.com/blog/post/2020/10/14/sc-right-to-default-bail-under-the-first-proviso-to-section-1672-crpc-not-a-mere-statutory-right-but-a-fundamental-right/> (last visited 28.02.2022).

¹⁴ In *Raghvendra Narvariya v. State of Chhattisgarh*, CRMP/ 43/2020, reported in ILR 2020 CG 759, the Hon'ble High Court affirmed that the once charge sheet is file, the indefeasible right of default bail accrued in

of statutory or default bail provided in proviso (a) to clause (2) of section 167 of CRPC is applicable in all cases of non-cognizable offences also, whether bailable or non-bailable. It further endeavours to state that the provisions of section 167 of CRPC have precedence over that of section 437 of CRPC in the matters of grant of bail because proviso (a) to clause (2) of section 167 of CRPC provides the maximum limit for pre-trial trial detention and thus, it is specific in nature.

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favour of accused get extinguished and referred to the following excerpt from the decision in *Rakesh Kumar Paul v. State of Assam*, (2017) 15 SCC 67 in paragraph 8 of the judgment that:

"44. Strong words indeed. That being so we are of the clear opinion that adapting this principle, it would equally be the duty and responsibility of a court on coming to know that the accused person before it is entitled to "default bail", to at least apprise him or her of the indefeasible right. A contrary view would diminish the respect for personal liberty, on which so much emphasis has been laid by this Court as is evidenced by the decisions mentioned above, and also adverted to in *Nirala Yadav*. (*Union of India v. Nirala Yadav*, (2014) 9 SCC 457)".